

against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The disk concentration of 100 µg/disk of all the compounds have been prepared using DMF as solvent.

The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1 and 2. The ir spectra of thiourea, where R=2-hydroxyphenyl show band at 1380 cm⁻¹ due to -NH-CS-NH- linkage and characteristic band at 3200 cm⁻¹ suggesting the presence of stretching vibration of OH group of salicylaldehyde moiety.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Bhavnagar University for research facilities and research scholarships (J.M.P. and M.P.D.) and to Dr. S. B. Trivedi, Director, Tuberculosis Research Centre, Amargadh for antitubercular and antibacterial testing facilities.

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Possible Antifertility Agents. Part-I. Synthesis of 2-(N,N-Substituted-aminomethyl)-3-(2-pyridyl)-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines

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Manuscript received 3-September 1983, revised 2 June 1984,
accepted 17 June 1984

SEVERAL quinazoline-4-one derivatives have been reported¹⁻³ to exhibit appreciable antifertility activity. Similarly, other heterocyclic systems with basic amine residues were also reported⁴⁻⁶ to exert antifertility action. Therefore, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise 2-(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-3-(2-pyridyl)-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines which incorporated these structural features (Scheme 1) and to study their antifertility action.

Scheme 1

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and uncorrected. Infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 137 infracord and Perkin Elmer 177 grating instruments. The pmr spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer R-3 spectrometer (90 MHz) in CDCl₃ and the chemical shift values are expressed in δ units using TMS as an internal standard.

2-Nitro-benz(2-pyridyl)amide (I): 2-Aminopyridine (1.88 g, 0.02 mol) and 2-nitrobenzoyl chloride (3.71 g, 0.02 mol) were refluxed in dry benzene in presence of triethylamine (6 ml, 0.04 mol) for 10 h (tlc). Triethylamine hydrochloride separated out was filtered and the filtrate on concentration yielded the crude amide which was recrystallised from ethanol (3.0 g, 62%), m.p. 150-52° (Found: N, 17.29%. C₁₃H₉N₃O₃ requires N, 17.28%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1350 and 1535 (N=O), 1595 (C=C), 1700 (C=O) and 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH stretching).

2-Amino-benz(2-pyridyl)amide (II): Hydrazine hydrate (40 ml) was carefully added to a solution of amide (I) (2.40 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) containing Raney nickel (0.5 g) for 4 h at room temperature. Then catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated to obtain the product (1.5 g, 70%), m.p. 130-31° (lit.⁷ 132-33°) (Found: N, 19.75%. C₁₃H₁₁N₃O requires N, 19.72%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1595 (C=C), 1680 (C=O) and 3300, 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH). The absence of peaks at 1380 and

1535 cm^{-1} (NO_2) further confirmed the complete reduction of the compound I.

2-N-Chloroacetyl-amino-benz(2-pyridyl)amide (III) : To a solution of amino compound (II) (1.07 g, 0.005 mol) in 50 ml chloroform, chloroacetyl chloride (0.75 ml, 0.01 mol) was added and left overnight at room temperature. Reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure which upon cooling yielded the product (1.0 g, 69%), m.p. 220-22 $^{\circ}$ d. (Found: N, 14.54%. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$ requires N, 14.51%); ν_{max} (KBr) 760 (C-Cl), 1595 (C=C), 1640 (C=O), 1680 (C=O), and 3100 cm^{-1} (NH).

2-Chloromethyl-3-(2-pyridyl)-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazoline (IV) : A solution of III (0.58 g, 0.002 mol) in 10 ml of acetic anhydride was refluxed for 7.5 h (tlc). The reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice and the solid separated was filtered and washed with water. The crude product was recrystallised from benzene/petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80 $^{\circ}$) (1:1) (0.36 g; 60%) m.p. 175-76 $^{\circ}$ (Found: N, 15.44%. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 15.47%); ν_{max} (KBr) 760 (C-Cl), 1595 (C=C), 1700 (C=O) and 2950 cm^{-1} (C-H methyl).

2-(N,N-Substituted aminomethyl)-3-(2-pyridyl)-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazoline (Va-e) : The chloro compound IV (0.543 g, 0.002 mol) and an appropriate secondary amine (0.0025 mol) were refluxed in 25 ml pyridine for 6-8 h (tlc). The excess of pyridine was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue poured over crushed ice. The crude product thus separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The compounds were characterised by their elemental analysis, m.ps., pmr spectra and the absence of C-Cl band at 760 cm^{-1} in their ir (KBr) spectra.

Biological screening : Method of Kamboj *et al.*⁸ was used to evaluate anti-implantation activity. However, none of these compounds showed any significant activity at an oral dose level of 25 mg/kg body weight.

TABLE I

Compd. no.	NR, R ₂	Molecular formula	M.p. $^{\circ}\text{C}$
Va	diethylamino-	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}$	304-06
Vb	pyrrolidino-	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{O}$	294-96
Vc	piperidino-	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}$	292-94
Vd	4-methyl-piperidino-	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}$	282-84
Ve	morpholino-	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$	298-800

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, for laboratory facilities, Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for providing spectral data and antifertility screening facilities and the U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance to one of the authors (S.H.R.A.).

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Possible Antifertility Agents. Part-II : Synthesis of 10,12-Substituted [1,4]-benzoxazino [3,4]-quinazolin-8-ones

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Manuscript received 12 September 1983, revised 2 June 1984,
accepted 17 June 1984

HIGH antifertility activity has been located among certain benz[a]anthracene derivatives¹ and also in substituted quinazolones²⁻⁴. Therefore, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise substituted [1,4]-benzoxazine [3,4]-quinazolin-8-ones which incorporated the essential structural skeleton of both classes of the compounds (Scheme 1) and to study their antifertility action.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and uncorrected. Infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on the Perkin Elmer 137 infracord instrument and the pmr spectra was recorded on the Perkin Elmer R-3 spectrometer (90 MHz) in trifluoroacetic acid and the chemical shift values were expressed in δ units using TMS as an internal standard.

2-(2-Nitrophenoxy methyl)-6,8-substituted-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-benzoxazines (Ia-d) : The compounds were synthesised according to the method of Sammour *et al.*⁵ 2-Nitrophenoxyacetic acid⁶ (2.98 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed with a large excess of thionyl chloride for 6 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off and its traces were removed by the azeotropic distillation with dry benzene (3 times). The acid chloride obtained was allowed to react with appropriate anthranilic acid (0.01 mol) in 10 ml dry pyridine at 0-5 $^{\circ}$ for 1 h. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The separated solid was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The crude product was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).